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Assessing the Impacts of Nature-Based Solutions on Ecosystem Services: A Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems Nexus Approach in the Nima River Sub-Basin (Colombia)

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Abstract: Forest ecosystem services are critical for maintaining ecological balance and supporting human well-being from different perspectives. However, rapid land use changes driven by agricultural expansion, urbanization, and industrial activities have significantly altered forest ecosystems, degrading the services they provide. We here conduct an ecosystem service assessment through biophysical and economic estimates for a multipurpose Andean water sub-basin in western Colombia. We compare a business as usual (BAU) with a forest nature-based solution (NbS) scenario focused on forest landscape restoration. The research employed participatory methods for the NbS selection and economic valuation techniques to evaluate water flow regulation, water provisioning, water purification, and food provisioning services. Results show that the NbS scenario yielded a net positive economic impact across most evaluated ecosystem services, with notable trade-offs. Specifically, the NbS scenario increased water retention by 2.9% compared to BAU. Water flow regulation demonstrated the most substantial economic benefit, increasing by EUR 11.39 million/year in the NbS scenario. On the other hand, the food provisioning service presented a reduction of EUR 3.2 million/year in the NbS scenario. These findings highlight the potential of forest-based NbS to address the Water–Energy–Food–Ecosystem (WEFE) nexus challenges. The study’s outcomes provide valuable insights for policymakers and practitioners, supporting the development of Payment for Ecosystem Services schemes and integrating ecosystem service valuation into land use planning and decision-making processes.

Keywords: WEFE nexus; trade-offs among ES; policy uptake of NbS; Valle del Cauca; ES valuation; forests ES

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1. Introduction

Forests play a crucial role in providing ecosystem services (ESs), critical for maintaining ecological balance and supporting human well-being through a wide range of functions. These include regulating services like carbon sequestration, habitat quality and biodiversity conservation, water regulation and soil preservation [1–5]. These ecosystems are integral to sustainable land use planning and decision-making due to their multifunctional role in providing critical ES and socio-economic benefits [6]. However, rapid land use changes driven by agricultural expansion, urbanization, and industrial activities—among other drivers—have significantly altered forests, leading to the degradation of these vital ecosystems and the services they provide [7]. Therefore, integrating measures to cope with these drivers along with forest management into land use planning is critical for achieving sustainable development goals and ensuring the balanced allocation of resources [8].

Forest loss and degradation are not evenly distributed across global regions. While Europe and Asia have gained forest cover during the last 10 years (0.3 and 1.2 million hectares (Mha)/year respectively), deforestation has happened mainly in the tropical regions in the global south, with net losses in Africa and South America of 3.9 and 2.6 Mha/year, respectively, between 2010 and 2020 [9]. One of the reasons forest loss continues in these regions is the different trade-offs that occur when promoting forest cover [10]. While some ESs of public nature, mainly regulating ones, might be enhanced (e.g., water quality, carbon sequestration, habitat for wild species), forest expansion can come with an opportunity cost by limiting other potentially profitable land uses and the enhancement of certain provisioning services, mostly of a private nature, such as agricultural food production [11]. This trade-off situation is particularly visible in Latin America, where forest loss trends continue [12]. Between 2000 and 2018, 68 Mha of net forest loss were registered in South America, primarily affecting tropical rainforests, which accounted for 40% of global forest loss during this period [13]. While having some of the most biodiverse forest ecosystems globally, the region also presents vast pressures on these resources driven by economic development targets and food and energy security agendas. Given its socio-economic context, the region must promote sustainable development and economic growth [14].

The continuous forest loss and degradation dynamics have increased the recognition of the need to implement sustainable land management practices to preserve and enhance forests and their ES. To promote such needed sustainable land management practices, nature-based solutions (NbSs) have emerged as a promising approach, as they are “actions to protect, conserve, restore, sustainably use and manage natural or modified terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine ecosystems, which address social, economic and environmental challenges effectively and adaptively, while simultaneously providing human well-being, ecosystem services and resilience and biodiversity benefits” [15]. Thus, NbSs should leverage natural processes to address environmental challenges while providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits [16]. Forest-related NbSs include reforestation, afforestation, sustainable forest management, and agroforestry systems [17].

NbSs can be framed within the Water–Energy–Food–Ecosystems (WEFE) nexus concept that, in recent years, has gained traction as a holistic framework for understanding the interconnections—either in terms of synergies or trade-offs—between these critical sectors [18]. The WEFE nexus highlights how water security is intrinsically linked to energy and food security and how ecosystem degradation can have far-reaching implications across these domains [19,20]. This concept is especially crucial for regions facing complex trade-offs between security agendas [21].

Despite the growing recognition of NbSs and the WEFE nexus and agreement about their potential interlinkages (e.g., [22,23]), there remains a significant research gap in understanding the positive and negative impacts that land use changes pushing for forest-related NbSs create. While advocacy increases for NbS, such as reforestation and afforestation, due to their capacity to sequester carbon and improve water-related ES, more research is needed into the unintended trade-offs that might arise, e.g., between provisioning and regulating services supply. Such research is necessary so that NbS strategies not only achieve climate and environmental objectives, but also support socioeconomic needs [24]. This research gap has become more pronounced in the Latin American region and other developing countries, where research lags behind and remains fragmented [25]. Specifically, there is a need to assess the costs and benefits these changes generate from multiple perspectives. Furthermore, it is essential to advance the practical application of ES valuation methodologies that inform decision-making linked to policy contexts, such as the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and climate change policies, to help direct funding for biodiversity conservation [26].

This study contributes to address these knowledge gaps by conducting a biophysical and economic valuation of ESs and comparing business as usual (BAU) and forest-NbS scenarios to identify and assess possible future land use development trajectories. The study was conducted within the context of the EU Horizon2020 REXUS project (Managing

REsilient neXUs Systems through participatory systems dynamics modeling; project co-funded by the European Union under the grant No. 101003632), which aimed to provide evidence on the role of NbS in facing WEFE nexus-related challenges in Europe and South America. More specifically, this research focuses on the Nima sub-basin in Colombia, a multipurpose Andean water sub-basin vital for water supply to the water, energy, and agricultural sectors in the municipality of Palmira, supporting 350,000 residents, 13 rural aqueducts and the municipal aqueduct, and two hydropower plants [27–29]. The sub-basin faces challenges such as deforestation, water pollution, and increased risks from climate change, necessitating the implementation of NbS. This area was set as a case study since strategic ecosystems for biodiversity conservation and hydrological cycle regulation are inside it, such as mist forests and paramo. In terms of biodiversity, the sub-basin accounts for around 566 species of faunal biodiversity, including birds, herpetofauna, and mammals [30]. Regarding water sources, the Nima River drainage network consists of 272 tributaries, covering approximately 96.65 km, providing drinking water to 13 rural communities and approximately 355,000 inhabitants of the Palmira municipality. Additionally, the area has around 127 springs and three glacial lakes [31].

By comparing the BAU scenario with an alternative forest-NbS future scenario, we expect to derive potential gains and losses associated with different land use and management choices. Our research results support and inform future decision-making regarding the implementation of forest-related NbS while contributing to advancing knowledge of using ES valuation as a tool within the WEFE nexus approach to support its practical implementation. This study aligns with the growing body of research on forests as NbSs, and their role in providing multiple ESs and benefits while also considering potential trade-offs in their implementation.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Description of the Study Area

The Nima River sub-basin, located in the Valle del Cauca Department in the western part of Colombia, covers 16,702 hectares and includes two main landscape units: a mountainous area upstream and a flat area downstream, with elevations ranging from 1050 to 4100 m above sea level (Figure 1). The climatic characteristics of the sub-basin are determined by an annual rainfall regime ranging from 1600 to 1800 mm [32]. Its hydrology is characterized by 14 tributaries, which provide an average flow of 2 m³/s, captured at the intake of the Palmira municipal aqueduct [33].

In terms of land use coverage in the sub-basin, the pristine paramo ecosystem and the Andean ecosystems (high mountain ecosystems) occupy 27% of the area and are home to various endemic and endangered species of fauna and flora. The main productive activity upstream is livestock farming, mainly cattle ranching, which accounts for 19% of the land use [34]. Forest plantations (*Pinus* sp. and *Eucalyptus* sp.) cover 2% of the area [35], and a mosaic of crops occupies another 3%, consisting mostly of coffee and annual crops (e.g., tomato, cilantro, green beans, onion, corn) [34]. The downstream area is surrounded by an agricultural landscape primarily composed of sugarcane plantations, covering 21% of the area [36].

In the mountainous upstream area of the sub-basin, there are designated conservation zones of regional and national importance, such as the Regional Natural Park of the Nima River, the National Natural Protective Forest Reserve of Amaime, and Las Herosas National Natural Park, where the Nima River originates [37]. In the lower area of the sub-basin, the Nima River flows into the Amaime River, one of the main tributaries of the Cauca River, the second most important river in Colombia.

Figure 1. Nima River sub-basin location and land covers. Own creation based on cartographic information system IDEAM (2018).

The sub-basin supports various economic activities across its area. In the upper part, these include commercial forestry, farming (e.g., poultry and pig farming), subsistence agriculture, and the cultivation of cash crops. Commercial crops, primarily sugar cane, dominate the lower part. These activities place pressures on essential ES, leading to significant issues, particularly related to water pollution and availability. As a result, water quality and quantity are among the primary ESs affected within the sub-basin [38].

2.2. NbS Selection

The NbSs chosen to simulate and compare with the current BAU scenario on the Nima River sub-basin were selected through a participatory process involving 30 stakeholders from different WEF sectors within the sub-basin, such as civil society and institutional bodies, as well as private sector organizations (Table 1). The selection of diversified types of stakeholders allowed us to consult actors with decision-making power, actors that would implement the discussed solutions, and actors that can facilitate or support the implementation process. These stakeholders included farmers; regional and local governments, such as the Municipality of Palmira through the departments of Environmental Management and Agriculture, and the Government of Valle del Cauca; the Chamber of Commerce of Palmira; the regional environmental authority; the National University of Colombia; and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) operating within the sugarcane sector and water-related associations, such as Fundación Fondo Agua por la Vida y la Sostenibilidad (i.e., the Water Fund Foundation) and the Association of Users of the Amaime and Nima Rivers (ASOAMAIME).

The participatory process, implemented within the framework of the REXUS project, employed a standardized methodology proposed by the REXUS consortium, consisting of two phases [39]. The first phase aimed at having the stakeholders select the NbS they considered capable of addressing the challenges of the sub-basin, from an initial list of solutions prioritized in the project's framework. In the second phase, a prioritization exercise of the selected NbS was conducted.

Table 1. Distribution of stakeholders by sector in the Nima River sub-basin NbS selection process.

Sector Represented	Number of Stakeholders
Agricultural sector	3
Energy companies	2
Local governments	5
Regional environmental authorities	3
Regional governments	2
Social organizations	7
Water associations	7
Water companies	1
Total stakeholders	30

During the first phase, stakeholders were given a list of 16 NbS, each accompanied by a description of its importance and the means for its implementation. The 16 NbS were selected within the framework of the REXUS project considering the two main challenges in the area. They analyzed these NbSs to determine which ones best addressed the challenges of the sub-basin. The challenges identified as of highest priority by stakeholders within the sub-basin are related to water quality and quantity regulation and maintenance. Additionally, stakeholders were encouraged to propose other NbSs they believed could address the challenges of the sub-basin that were not included in the provided list. This participatory approach yielded several stakeholder-identified solutions, which were subsequently included in the final list of NbS (see Table 6 in Section 3).

In the second phase of the participatory process, stakeholders were asked to qualitatively prioritize the selected NbSs, according to their knowledge and using the following three criteria:

- *Effectiveness*, i.e., the solution's effectiveness in achieving the goals and objectives defined to face WEFE nexus-related challenges;
- *Acceptability*, i.e., the level of social acceptance the solution has;
- *Feasibility*, i.e., how easily the solution can be implemented based on the stakeholders' capabilities.

At the end of the prioritization exercise, stakeholders agreed to select forest landscape restoration, via afforestation and reforestation practices, as the single most relevant NbS at the local scale to face the challenges of the sub-basin. The subsequent NbS assessment, therefore, has been applied considering such NbSs as an alternative to the BAU scenario.

2.3. Ecosystem Services Assessment

2.3.1. Scenarios Definition

Building on the outcomes of the stakeholder consultation process, a forest landscape restoration strategy via a hypothetical expansion of forest areas in the middle and upper parts of the sub-basin was identified as the best alternative land use scenario to the BAU.

To conduct the analysis, two scenarios were defined (Figure 2):

1. **Baseline (BAU) Scenario**—This scenario includes the current land use practices without any additional conservation measures or any change of practices. With the term “current”, we indicate the time in which the study has been conducted, and it reflects the traditional management practices in the sub-basin. In this scenario, fragmented forests and grasslands are prevalent on the upper part of the sub-basin;
2. **NbS Scenario**—This scenario includes the establishment and development of dense forests of native species between the middle and upper parts of the sub-basin, incorporating the prioritized forest landscape restoration strategies. Example species include Andean trees and shrubs from low montane humid forest such as the native pepper plants (e.g., *Piper cornifolium*, *P. lacunosum*), Andean walnut (*Juglans neotropica*), Cecropia trees (*Cecropia* sp.), *Alnus acuminata*, *Morella pubescens*, and others [40].

Figure 2. Land covers for the (a) BAU and (b) NbS scenarios.

These two scenarios were mapped using Geographic Information Systems (GIS), considering areas with high potential for Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES) implementation, considering the previous identification of potential areas to reforest through this scheme by the Palmira municipality. We assessed water flow regulation, water quality and water provisioning ES for each scenario using the InVEST 3.13.0 flood risk mitigation, nutrient-delivery ration and annual water yield models, respectively [41]. Additionally, we also considered the value of food (i.e., farmed food-crop) provisioning for both scenarios. The selected ESs were chosen based on the primary challenges and main economic activities within the area. The NbS scenario has been considered as the forest was at the maturity stage, providing the full range of potential ES. To account for the time that the NbS takes to deliver the ES, we created a cashflow and estimated a net present value (NPV) for the NbS scenario, considering the annual costs of implementing the NbS (i.e., payments to landowners during ten years within the PES framework) and its expected benefits from year 11, considering a 25-year horizon. We used a discount rate of 4% following [42]. The value of the annual costs of implementing the NbS was retrieved during conversations with the Municipality of Palmira within the framework of the REXUS project. The resulting NPV was transformed into a single annuity for a terminating annual series. This step makes NbS values comparable with the BAU ones. Following the “with and without” principle [43,44], net ES supply was calculated as the difference between the NbS and BAU scenarios.

2.3.2. Valuation Models

For both BAU and NbS scenarios, four key ESs were assessed from both biophysical (Section 3.2.1) and economic (Section 3.2.2) perspectives. This evaluation allows for an understanding of the impact of land use changes on the ecosystem from the different WEFE dimensions.

The assessment of ESs and the methodologies used for each of them are detailed below.

1. Water flow regulation.

Biophysical Assessment—The flood risk mitigation capacity was assessed using the InVEST 3.14.1 flood risk mitigation model, which allows one to measure the capacity of ecosystems to retain precipitation water and release it in a controlled manner, regulating drought and flood events. This model has been previously applied in economic valuation studies of NbS, where it effectively demonstrated their economic benefits to flood risk management [44,45];

Economic Valuation—The economic value of water flow regulation was estimated using the replacement cost method, which calculates the cost of alternative flood mitigation infrastructure, such as levees and retention basins, that would be required to achieve similar outcomes. The annual value of the ES was calculated as the single annuity of a finite series of annuities, based on a useful life of 60 years for the surrogate good and a discount rate of 4% [42].

Input and output data for assessing and evaluating water flow regulation are reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Input and output data for the assessment and evaluation of water flow regulation.

Input Data	Description
Land cover map (BAU and Nbs scenarios)	BAU: Raster of land use/land cover (LULC) for each pixel (resolution 5 m × 5 m), based on [36] NbS: BAU map adapted with prioritized areas for a PES scheme from the municipality of Palmira
Biophysical table	csv file reporting Curve number (CN) values for each LULC type and each hydrological group; CN values were derived from [46]
Depth of rainfall (mm)	71.4 mm as the average maximum precipitation in 24 h (1989–2019), identified from [47]
Soils' hydrological group raster	250 m spatial resolution raster of categorical hydrological groups from [48]
Economic value	Replacement cost method. Surrogate good: lamination basin. Unit cost: EUR 400/m ³ calculated from [49] and updated to 2023
Output data	Description
Retained runoff volume (m ³)	Raster with runoff retention values (in m ³) indicating the capability of each pixel to store runoff

2. Water provisioning.

Biophysical Assessment—The quantity of water provided under the BAU and NbS scenarios was assessed using the InVEST 3.14.1 annual water yield model. This tool evaluates how land cover changes impact water availability throughout the year.

Economic Valuation—The market price method was used to assess the economic value of water provisioning, calculating the potential revenue generated from water use for various purposes such as hydropower, agricultural, and domestic.

Input and output data for assessing and evaluating water provisioning are reported in Table 3.

3. Water purification.

Biophysical Assessment—The InVEST 3.14.1 nutrient delivery ratio model was used to assess the sub-basin's capacity to filter and purify water by trapping nitrogen exports, based on the present land cover for each scenario.

Economic Valuation—The economic benefits of water purification were estimated using avoided-cost methods, focusing on the expenses avoided in water treatment facilities due to the natural purification services provided by ecosystems.

Input and output data for assessing and evaluating water purification are reported in Table 4.

Table 3. Input and output data for the assessment and evaluation of water provisioning.

Input Data	Description
Land cover map (BAU and NbS scenarios)	BAU: Raster of land use/land cover (LULC) for each pixel (resolution 5 m × 5 m), based on [36] NbS: BAU map adapted with prioritized areas for a PES scheme from the municipality of Palmira
Precipitation map	Raster of average annual precipitation in the sub-basing, retrieved from [50]
Evapotranspiration map	Raster of average annual evapotranspiration in the sub-basin, retrieved from [51]
Root restricting layer depth map	Raster of root restricting layer depth, the soil depth at which root penetration is strongly inhibited because of physical or chemical characteristics, retrieved from [52]
Plant available water content	Raster of plant available water content, the fraction of water that can be stored in the soil profile that is available to plants. Value defined as 1, as per the suggestion of the InVEST model
Biophysical table	csv file reporting biophysical parameters for each LULC class; parameters were derived from [51,52]
Economic value (EUR)	Market price from water use for hydropower, agricultural, and domestic purposes; data from [53] in COP and converted to EUR
Output Data	Description
Water yield volume (m ³)	Raster values with the total volume of water yield in the sub-basin (in m ³)

Table 4. Input and output data for the assessment and evaluation of water purification.

Input Data	Description
Land cover map (BAU and NbS scenarios)	BAU: Raster of land use/land cover (LULC) for each pixel (resolution 5 m × 5 m), based on [36] NbS: BAU map adapted with prioritized areas for a PES scheme from the municipality of Palmira
Digital Elevation Model	Raster of elevation above sea level for the study area; data from [54]
Nutrient Runoff Proxy	Raster of average annual precipitation in the sub-basin, retrieved from [50]
Biophysical table	csv file reporting each LULC class in relation to its biophysical properties to N load and retention; values were derived from [55,56]
Economic value	Replacement cost method. Surrogate good: lamination basin. Unit cost: EUR 87.6/kg of N; data retrieved from [57] in COP and converted to EUR and updated to 2023.
Output Data	Description
Total N export (kg/m ² /year)	A raster showing how much nitrogen from each pixel eventually reaches the stream for each scenario

4. Food provisioning.

Biophysical Assessment—An Excel-based calculation was conducted to estimate changes in food production under different scenarios, considering the area of arable land and crop yield data.

Economic Valuation—The economic value of food provisioning was evaluated using market prices, considering the potential revenue from different agricultural products sales.

Input and output data for assessing and evaluating food provisioning are reported in Table 5.

Table 5. Input and output data for the assessment and evaluation of food provisioning.

Input Data	Description
Products	List of agricultural products harvested in the Nima River sub-basin; data retrieved from [34]
Price per kg and ton (EUR/kg and EUR/ton)	The price of the product per kilogram and ton in COP retrieved from [58] and converted into EUR
Farmed area in Nima (ha)	The area where each product is cultivated within the Nima River sub-basin; data calculated via Q-GIS based on the land cover maps
Output Data	Description
Total crop production in the Nima basin (ton)	The total production quantity of each product, based on the harvested area and yield
Total value (EUR)	The total market value of the production from the Nima River sub-basin in EUR, calculated by multiplying the production quantity by the price per ton

3. Results

This section presents the outcomes of the participatory process that selected and prioritized the most relevant NbS to conduct the ES valuation in the Nima sub-basin (Section 3.1) and the findings from such biophysical and economic valuations for both the BAU and NbS scenarios (Section 3.2).

3.1. Results from the Participatory Process and Selection of the Most Relevant NbS

The participatory process with WEFE-relevant stakeholders focused on proposing and prioritizing NbS. As a result of this process, 11 NbSs were considered relevant to face the challenges of the sub-basin (i.e., water quality and quantity). Moreover, stakeholders proposed to add four extra measures they considered relevant. Subsequently, among the total 15 NbSs selected, stakeholders prioritized 5 of them using the criteria mentioned in the methodology section (Section 2.2). Forest landscape restoration was the final solution prioritized as the most relevant by the stakeholders (Table 6 synthesizes the process of NbS selection and prioritization, from the initial list proposed to the final NbS selected).

3.2. Valuation of NbSs' Impacts on Ecosystem Services

The assessment of targeted ESs associated to both the BAU and NbS scenarios was conducted through a two-step process. First, ESs were assessed in biophysical terms (Section 3.2.1) and an economic analysis was performed to quantify the economic impacts of the two scenarios (Section 3.2.2).

3.2.1. Biophysical Valuation of ES

The biophysical assessment estimated that 233,143 m³ of water is retained annually when comparing the BAU scenario with the NbS scenario (Table 7). This result indicates a 2.9% increase in water retention for the NbS scenario (i.e., implementing the forest landscape restoration strategy via the PES scheme). Conversely, the evaluation of water provision showed a minimal increase of 0.01% in the volume of surface water available per

year, from 157.12 million m³/year in the BAU scenario to 157.14 million m³/year in the NbS scenario.

Table 6. List of NbS discussed with stakeholders and measures prioritized.

List of NbS proposed to stakeholders	
Conservation of natural areas	**
Forest landscape restoration	***
Restoring buffer vegetation lines on crop and river edges	**
Silvopastoral systems	**
Agroecological practices	*
Agroforestry systems	*
Cover crops	*
Creation of ponds to trap sediments and agricultural pollution runoff	*
Crop rotation	*
Use of organic fertilizers and pesticides	*
Wetlands for wastewater treatment	*
Floodplain restoration and management	
Limit or prevent specific uses and practices	
Soil and slope revegetation	
Stream reconnection	
Water improvement and efficiency measures in agriculture	
List of solutions proposed by the stakeholders	
Environmental education	**
Payment for ecosystem services (PES)	*
Community-managed projects	
Proper planning for responsible nature tourism	

* NbS selected by the stakeholders from the initial list. ** NbSs prioritized by stakeholders. *** NbSs selected for the ES valuation.

Table 7. Biophysical valuation of ES provided in a BAU vs. NbS scenario.

Ecosystem Services	Tools Used for the Valuation	Biophysical Valuation				Unit
		BAU Scenario	NbS Scenario	NbS—BAU	% Change	
Water flow regulation	InVEST (urban flood risk mitigation)	8,158,519.12	8,391,661.75	233,142.63	2.86	m ³ retained/year
Water provisioning	InVEST (annual water yield)	157,123,309.34	157,137,693.93	14,384.59	0.01	m ³ /year
Water purification	Invest (nutrient delivery ratio)	35,761.52	34,071.72	−1689.80	−4.73	Nitrogen export (kg/year)
Food provisioning	Excel	474,250.11	470,506.34	−3743.77	−0.79	Tons of food/year

Water quality assessment indicates a 4.7% reduction in nitrogen pollutants (kg/year) when transitioning from the BAU scenario to the NbS scenario. This result highlights the potential positive impact of forest landscape restoration in lowering water pollution levels. On the other hand, the food production service showed a reduction in the NbS scenario concerning the BAU one since part of the forest landscape restoration strategy was simulated in current agricultural lands. The biophysical assessment estimated total crop production to be 474,250.11 ton/year under the BAU scenario and 470,506.34 ton/year under the NbS scenario. These results imply a 3743.77 ton/year reduction, equivalent to a decrease of nearly 0.8% in service provision.

3.2.2. Economic Valuation of ES

The economic valuation exercise estimates significant differences between the BAU and NbS scenarios. The values reported consist of single annuities of terminating annual series for both scenarios calculated based on a 25-year horizon (Table 8).

Table 8. Economic valuation of ES provided by the BAU and NbS scenarios.

Ecosystem Services	Economic Valuation					Unit
	Methods	BAU Scenario	NbS Scenario	NbS—BAU	% Change	
Water flow regulation	Replacement costs	144,248,639.43	155,639,727.66	11,391,088.23	7.90	EUR/year for water retained
Water provisioning	Market price	350,971.83	370,701.26	19,729.43	5.68	EUR/year for water available
Water purification	Avoided costs	3,249,406.41	2,983,626.45	265,779.97 *	8.18 *	EUR/year for water purified
Food provisioning	Market price	37,199,890.56	33,986,966.86	−3,212,923.70	−8.64	EUR/year for food produced
Total				8,463,673.93		EUR/year

* Value assumed to be positive since it represents avoided costs via ES provisioning.

Water flow regulation emerges as the ES with the most substantial increase under the NbS scenario, showing an increase of EUR 11.39 million/year compared to the BAU scenario, with a total value of EUR 155.64 million/year. The water provisioning service displays a comparative minimal difference between the two scenarios, yielding an increase of EUR 19,729.43/year in the NbS scenario over the BAU, with total values of EUR 370,701.26/year and EUR 350,971.83/year, respectively. This marginal difference aligns with the minor variation observed from the biophysical assessment. Regarding the water purification service, the estimated avoided costs for water purification show a moderate decrease under the NbS scenario, which reflects the positive effect of the NbS for this service. The economic benefit is estimated at EUR 265,779.96/year in terms of avoided costs with respect to the BAU scenario. On the other hand, the food provisioning service shows a decrease in the NbS scenario. The economic valuation indicates a reduction of EUR 3,212,923.70/year compared to the BAU scenario, contrary to the other services. This economic decrease corresponds with the reduction observed in the biophysical assessment of this service.

These assessments estimate that the NbS scenario results in a net positive economic impact of EUR 8,463,673.93/year across all evaluated ESs.

4. Discussion

The biophysical and economic valuation results of this study provide valuable insights into the potential impacts of implementing NbSs in the Nima sub-basin in Colombia with a WEF nexus approach. Our estimations show that the forest-based NbS scenario results in a net positive economic impact of EUR 8.46 million/year across all evaluated ESs. This finding aligns with other studies that have shown the economic benefits of NbSs, such as [59], who report significant economic advantages of forest-NbSs through the supply of multiple ESs, among which are water flow regulation and water quality. Other studies like [60] report a significant increase in carbon sequestration through forest conservation and restoration. We observed reduced food provision at the expense of increased water flow regulation and purification. Interestingly, our results show a slight increase (0.01%) in annual water quantity, differing from some studies that suggest forest restoration might reduce overall water availability in a basin [61] and, in more general terms, suggest a strong relationship between forest cover and change in runoff patterns, e.g., [62]. On the other hand, our findings are consistent with those of [63], who found that reforestation measures

can reduce peak flows and stormflows associated with soil degradation; however, they did not report evidence that this also produced a corresponding increase in low flows. Although the dominant paradigm indicates trade-offs between forest cover and water yield, particularly in terms of groundwater recharge, [64] identified several caveats and biases. While these inconsistent findings may advocate for more specific studies, they may also suggest that some issues arose in feeding or calibrating relevant InVEST models.

Our study contributes to addressing knowledge gaps about forest-NbS scenarios in multipurpose water basins, which are critical for water supply to various sectors. This approach serves as an instrument for considering different elements of the WEF nexus, highlighting potential synergies and trade-offs across sectors. For instance, the reduction in food provision indicated by our valuation might raise concerns among some stakeholders (e.g., farmers) in the municipality of Palmira, mainly if restoration is applied to the entire middle and upper zones of the sub-basin where agriculture is relevant for local livelihoods [65].

The participatory process employed in this study plays a crucial role in legitimizing the results and enhancing their potential for integration into decision-making processes. This approach coincides with the growing recognition of the importance of stakeholder engagement in ES assessment and valuation, aligning theoretical models with the interests of local governments and other stakeholders [66,67]. In this way, our findings can significantly contribute to decision-making related to agricultural conversion projects in strategic zones of the Nima River sub-basin, potentially enabling these projects to be integrated into the implemented PES program.

The potential effectiveness of this exercise in promoting PES schemes for forest landscape restoration is significant. By quantifying the economic value of ES under different scenarios, our study provides a strong foundation for justifying investments in NbSs. This approach is similar to that used by [68] in their analysis of PES schemes in Costa Rica, where economic valuation played a crucial role in program design and implementation. Our findings, showing increases in water flow regulation and water purification services, align with other successful PES cases in Latin America, such as the Water Funds in Ecuador and Colombia [69]. Globally, our results contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting the use of economic valuation in PES scheme development, as seen in cases from Vietnam [70] and Tanzania [71].

Despite the valuable insights provided by this study, several limitations should be acknowledged. Data availability was a significant constraint, necessitating reliance on global sources that might not be accurately calibrated to the study area. This limitation is common in ecosystem service valuation studies, as noted by [2]. Additionally, our analysis focused on a subset of forest ES, potentially underestimating the total value of NbS implementation. For instance, carbon sequestration could significantly increase the estimated benefits, as [72] demonstrated in their global forest carbon assessment. Forests also provide other significant regulating services, such as moisture recycling and temperature regulation, which might influence other land cover responses (e.g., agriculture). The study by [73] reported that nearly 50% of precipitation in certain regions is regulated by vegetation, and studies by [74,75] demonstrated how forests effectively contribute to global and local cooling by driving evapotranspiration, creating cloud cover, and influencing surface albedo. These ESs provided by forests play a critical role in sustaining agricultural productivity downwind from forested areas. Similarly, ESs that might reveal additional economic advantages from forest conservation and restoration are pollination and biological control services, as [76] showed in their study on coffee production in Costa Rica.

Despite these limitations, this study can provide substantial policy implications for land use planning and ES management. Our findings support the mobilization of Target 19 of the Global Biodiversity Framework, which aims to increase financial resources for biodiversity conservation. This study provides a strong argument for integrating ecosystem service valuation into land planning processes by demonstrating the economic value of NbSs. This narrative aligns with the recommendations of [77], who argue for mainstream-

ing natural capital approaches in decision-making. Furthermore, our results can inform the development of more comprehensive PES schemes and support the implementation of NbSs at larger scales, contributing to both local sustainable development and global conservation goals.

5. Conclusions

We conducted a biophysical and economic valuation of ES to compare BAU and forest-NbS scenarios to estimate potential benefits and trade-offs of land use development trajectories with a WEFE nexus approach in a multipurpose Andean water sub-basin in Western Colombia. Our estimations show that the forest-based NbS scenario results in significant net positive economic impacts across all evaluated ESs, yet highlights relevant trade-offs between ESs (e.g., food provisioning). From a public policy perspective, such a scenario looks fully consistent with the rationale behind policy tools and—in particular—market-based instruments to support ES delivery. Indeed, the NbS scenario would support the provision of a set of public goods, benefiting local communities as a whole, at the (partial) expense of private goods (food). The estimated gap in terms of benefits gained under the NbS scenario provides robust justification for the NbS development from a public investment angle, as it demonstrates it would be possible to support farmers in partly shifting land use and management practices towards solutions benefiting society at large, including beyond the targeted area. In fact, the benefits gained under the NbS scenario, in terms of water flow regulation, water quality, and water quantity, could contribute to reducing the main water-related challenges affecting farmers in the upper part of the sub-basin.

The study builds on a participatory process involving stakeholders from different WEFE sectors within the sub-basin, who prioritized and selected the NbS scenario to compare against the BAU one, enhancing community participation and the potential integration of this exercise into potential decision-making processes. ESs for both scenarios were assessed from both biophysical and economic perspectives, considering ES representing different WEFE dimensions.

Our study supports the growing body of literature on the economic benefits of forest-NbSs, and can provide policy implications for land use planning and ecosystem services management. Specifically, our findings could support the mobilization of important global environmental goals, such as Target 19 of the Global Biodiversity Framework. Our results can inform the development of PES schemes and support the implementation of NbSs at larger scales, contributing to both local sustainable development and global conservation goals.

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